

ANALYSIS OF SOCIOLOGICAL ASPECTS: EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES AND FINANCIAL BENEFITS FOR SMALL POULTRY KEEPING ENTREPRENEURS IN THE MID-TERAI REGION OF NEPAL

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Cite This Article: Rudra Kumari Timilsina, Mayanath Ghimire, A. K. Mishra, Eka Bahadur Shrestha, Shukra Raj Adhikari & A. Dinesh Kumar, "Analysis of Sociological Aspects: Employment Opportunities and Financial Benefits for Small Poultry Keeping Entrepreneurs in the Mid-Terai Region of Nepal", *International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research*, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 56-63, 2024.

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DOI:

Abstract:

Purpose: This study aims to evaluate the impact of poultry keeping entrepreneurship on employment and income among residents of the mid-Terai region of Nepal.

Methodology: The research focused on broiler poultry-keeping farmers in the mid-Terai area. A structured questionnaire was designed and face-to-face interviews were conducted to collect data. Poultry farm owners were selected using a purposive sampling technique to ensure a representative sample.

Findings and Results: The analysis indicates that poultry production is a highly profitable venture in the mid-Terai region. Broiler farming, in particular, has been identified as a lucrative short-term farming activity in rural areas. The study found that managing 100 broiler poultry can generate an annual income of approximately NPR 800,000 to NPR 900,000, with a net profit of NPR 320,000. Additionally, poultry farming provides employment opportunities for two individuals.

Key Words: Disease, Enterprises, Employment, Income, Poultry

1. Introduction

Poultry keeping has been practiced in Nijgadh, Bara, for some time, yet no prior research or publications exist on poultry farming in this specific area. This study focuses on Nijgadh Ward No. 6, where Kumar Acharya, a local farmer, manages a small-scale poultry farm with 100 birds. The study aims to explore the types of employment opportunities and benefits derived from poultry farming, particularly among small-scale farmers in the mid-Terai region of Bara District, Nepal. Globally, livestock production plays a significant role in agriculture. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), cattle farming alone contributes 20-24% to the agricultural gross domestic product (AGDP) in both developed and developing countries. Over 600 million households worldwide rely on cattle farming as a primary income source. Livestock products, including eggs, milk, and meat, are crucial for providing high-quality protein and essential micronutrients such as vitamins A, B12, riboflavin, calcium, iron, and zinc, which are often deficient in plant-based diets. The FAO projects that the demand for livestock products will increase by over 50% by 2050 due to population growth, with significant demand spikes expected in Africa and South Asia (Poudel et al., 2020).

In Nepal, poultry farming is growing rapidly, with two predominant production systems: scavenging and intensive. Scavenging poultry is common in rural areas, with native flocks representing nearly 45% of the total poultry population, while commercial poultry makes up the remaining 55%. The commercial poultry sector has expanded significantly from 1985 to 2014, tripling its output to meet urban demand for meat and eggs (Acharya & Kafle, 2015). Poultry farming offers distinct advantages over other agricultural enterprises, including a relatively low-cost source of protein, a short production cycle, and the ability to integrate with other farming practices.

The poultry industry is a cornerstone of Nepal's agricultural sector, contributing approximately 4% to the national GDP. Despite impressive growth in chicken production, the sector remains heavily reliant on medication, particularly vaccinations, and essential feed ingredients. Poultry farming is a vital source of income and employment, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas (Poudel et al., 2020). Research by Adhikari et al. (2023) highlights that poultry meat contributes around 4% to Nepal's GDP. The study reviews Nepal's poultry population, production, and distribution. In the past decade, commercial chicken production has more than doubled, driven by rising demand for poultry products. Nepal ranks 112th globally in chicken meat production and 92nd in egg production. Data from 2021-2022 show poultry meat production at 65,387 tons, growing at an average annual rate of 6.60%. According to Yadhav and Yadhav (2021), the poultry industry is one of Nepal's most dynamic agricultural sectors, expanding at an annual rate of 17-18%. Poultry products, due to their affordability and high protein content, are increasingly popular across all demographics, irrespective of caste, creed, or age. Poultry farming at the local level in Nepal, particularly within residential areas, has seen a modest expansion. However, commercial broiler poultry farming faces significant challenges that impact its sustainability and growth. This analysis delves into the primary issues confronting small-scale broiler and egg

production farmers in Nepal, which include competition for resources, high production costs, disease management, technical inefficiencies, genetic limitations, climate change impacts, and market instability.

Competition with Human and Animal Food Sources: One of the pressing issues for broiler poultry farming in Nepal is the competition for feed resources. Poultry farmers often face challenges in securing affordable and high-quality feed due to competition with human consumption and other animal farming sectors. This competition drives up feed prices, which significantly impacts the overall cost of poultry production.

High Cost of Production: The cost of poultry production in Nepal is elevated due to several factors, including expensive feed, veterinary care, and infrastructure. These costs are compounded by the need for specialized inputs, such as high-quality vaccines and medications, which are often costly. The high production costs strain the profitability of poultry farms, particularly small-scale operations that have limited financial resources.

Disease Management Challenges: Disease outbreaks are a critical concern in poultry farming. Small-scale farmers often struggle with inadequate access to veterinary services and lack of technical expertise to manage and prevent diseases. The high cost of vaccines and the scarcity of qualified technicians in rural areas exacerbate these issues. In severe cases, disease outbreaks can result in significant poultry losses, leading to substantial financial setbacks and, in some cases, complete business failure.

Low Technical Efficiency: Many poultry farms in Nepal operate with low technical efficiency. This inefficiency is due to a combination of factors, including outdated farming practices, insufficient knowledge about advanced poultry management techniques, and limited access to modern technologies. As a result, productivity levels are lower, and farms struggle to compete with more technologically advanced operations.

Lack of Genetic Improvement: The genetic quality of local poultry breeds in Nepal often falls short of commercial standards. There is a lack of focused breeding programs to improve the economic traits of local breeds, such as growth rates, egg production, and disease resistance. This genetic limitation affects the overall productivity and profitability of poultry farming.

Adverse Climatic Conditions: Climate change poses a significant threat to poultry farming in Nepal. Adverse climatic conditions, such as extreme temperatures and unpredictable weather patterns, can negatively impact poultry health and productivity. Farmers must invest in additional infrastructure and management practices to mitigate these effects, further increasing production costs.

Market Instability: The market for poultry products, including eggs and meat, is unstable. Fluctuations in prices and demand can create financial uncertainty for farmers. This instability is often driven by factors such as market oversupply, import competition, and changing consumer preferences. The unpredictable market conditions make it difficult for farmers to plan and sustain their operations effectively.

Vaccine Expenses and Lack of Technicians: The cost of vaccines is a significant expense for poultry farmers, especially given the high prevalence of diseases. Additionally, the scarcity of trained veterinary professionals in rural areas further complicates disease management. The absence of local technicians means that farmers often have to travel long distances for veterinary services, increasing their operational costs and complicating timely intervention during disease outbreaks.

2. Statement of the Problem:

The challenges faced by poultry farmers in Nepal are multifaceted and impact the sustainability and profitability of the sector. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach, including improving feed resource management, reducing production costs through subsidies or support programs, enhancing disease management and technical support, investing in genetic improvements, and developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change. Additionally, stabilizing the poultry market and increasing the availability of veterinary services are crucial steps towards ensuring the long-term viability of poultry farming in Nepal. By tackling these challenges, Nepal can better support its poultry farmers and enhance the overall efficiency and resilience of the sector.

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the poultry farming sector in Nijgadh, Bara, highlighting its economic potential and employment benefits for small-scale farmers. The rapid growth of poultry production in Nepal, driven by rising demand and a shift towards more intensive production methods, underscores the sector's importance in the national economy. Poultry farming not only enhances food security by providing affordable protein sources but also generates significant employment opportunities. The findings from Nijgadh can serve as a model for similar regions, emphasizing the need for targeted research and policy interventions to support and expand poultry farming in Nepal.

3. Objective:

The primary objective of this analysis is to assess how small poultry keeping enterprises contribute to employment generation and financial stability for entrepreneurs in the Mid-Terai region. This evaluation aims to provide insights into the economic benefits and employment opportunities created by poultry farming in this specific area.

4. Methodology:

The study focused on a specific demographic within the Mid-Terai region of Nepal. The selected participants were small poultry entrepreneurs, specifically Brahmin caste farmers, who manage poultry enterprises with approximately 100 birds each. This targeted selection was based on the following criteria:

Caste and Regional Focus:

- The study was confined to Brahmin caste farmers to explore the impact of poultry farming within a specific social group. This demographic focus was chosen to understand the particular needs, challenges, and benefits experienced by this community in the Mid-Terai region.

Scale of Poultry Farming:

- The research concentrated on small-scale poultry keepers with an average flock size of 100 birds. This scale was selected to represent typical small poultry enterprises in the region and to ensure that the study could provide insights applicable to similar small-scale operations.

Data Collection Methodology:

The data collection process was designed to gather comprehensive and reliable information from the selected poultry entrepreneurs. The following methods were used:

Structured Semi-Questionnaires:

- A structured semi-questionnaire was developed to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness in data collection. The questionnaire was designed to capture various aspects of poultry farming, including:
 - Demographic Information: Details about the farmers, such as age, gender, and educational background.
 - Poultry Management Practices: Information on feeding, housing, and disease management.
 - Economic Aspects: Data on income, expenses, profit margins, and financial challenges.
 - Employment Impact: Insights into the number and types of jobs created by the poultry enterprises.
 - Challenges and Opportunities: Information on difficulties faced, such as disease outbreaks and market fluctuations, as well as potential opportunities for improvement.
- The semi-structured format allowed for both quantitative and qualitative responses, providing a deeper understanding of the nuances of poultry farming in this specific context.

Face-to-Face Interviews:

- Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the selected poultry entrepreneurs to collect primary data. This method was chosen for its effectiveness in:
 - Building Rapport: Establishing a trusting relationship with participants to encourage open and honest responses.
 - Clarifying Responses: Allowing interviewers to clarify questions and gather detailed explanations where necessary.
 - Observational Data: Providing opportunities to observe farm conditions and practices directly, enriching the data collection process with contextual insights.

Data Analysis:

The collected data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods:

- This analysis provided measurable insights into the financial benefits and employment opportunities associated with small poultry enterprises.
- This analysis helped in understanding the broader context of poultry farming practices and their impact on the farmers.

The methodology employed in this study-focusing on a specific demographic of Brahmin caste small poultry entrepreneurs in the Mid-Terai region-ensured a detailed and contextually relevant analysis. By using structured semi-questionnaires and face-to-face interviews, the study was able to gather comprehensive data on the economic and employment impacts of poultry farming, providing valuable insights into the viability and challenges of small-scale poultry enterprises in this region of Nepal.

5. Literature Review:

Poultry farming is a significant agricultural activity that contributes to global food security and local economies. This analysis examines the sociological aspects of poultry keeping among Brahmin caste farmers in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal. The focus is on the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of poultry farming, as well as the enforcement mechanisms in place to address these challenges.

5.1 ABCDE Analysis:

Advantages:

- **Economic Benefits:** Poultry farming offers substantial economic advantages, including a reliable source of income. For Brahmin farmers in the Mid-Terai region, poultry farming can be a profitable venture, providing a steady revenue stream from the sale of eggs and meat. Research indicates that broiler poultry farming can generate significant income, with earnings reaching up to 8–9 lakh NRs annually and net profits around 3,20,000 NRs per year (Rayo, 2020; Gržinić, 2023).
- **Employment Opportunities:** Poultry farming creates employment opportunities for local residents. In the case of the Brahmin farmers, the activity provides full-time jobs for at least two people, often including family members (Dersjant-Li et al., 2015). This contributes to reducing unemployment and enhancing the economic stability of rural households.
- **Nutritional Benefits:** Poultry farming plays a crucial role in improving nutritional standards. Poultry products such as eggs and meat are rich sources of high-quality protein and essential micronutrients, which are vital for human health (Fanatico, 2009; Singh et al., 2022).

Benefits:

- **Community Integration:** Poultry farming fosters community integration and cooperation. Farmers often share knowledge, resources, and support with each other, creating a sense of community and collective problem-solving (Miao, 2005).
- **Income Diversification:** Poultry farming provides a means of diversifying income sources. For Brahmin farmers, integrating poultry into their agricultural practices helps mitigate financial risks associated with crop farming and enhances overall economic resilience (Fitsum, 2014).
- **Market Demand:** The growing market demand for poultry products, driven by increasing urban populations and changing dietary preferences, offers a favorable environment for poultry farming (Otte et al., 2021). This demand supports the viability and growth of poultry enterprises in the region.

Constraints:

- **High Production Costs:** Poultry farming is associated with high production costs, including expenses for feed, vaccines, and management (Cervantes, 2015). The financial burden of these inputs can affect profitability and sustainability.

- Disease Management: Poultry farms are vulnerable to diseases, which can lead to significant losses. The lack of access to veterinary services and effective disease management strategies exacerbates the risks associated with poultry farming (Conan et al., 2012; Gržinić, 2022).
- Environmental Impact: Intensive poultry farming contributes to environmental challenges, including waste management issues and greenhouse gas emissions (Gržinić, 2023). Proper waste management practices are essential to mitigate the environmental impact.

Disadvantages:

- Market Fluctuations: The poultry market is subject to fluctuations in prices, which can create financial uncertainty for farmers. Volatile market conditions can impact the stability of income and profitability (Rayo, 2020).
- Biosecurity Risks: Low biosecurity measures in backyard poultry farming increase the risk of disease outbreaks, which can have devastating effects on poultry health and productivity (Conan et al., 2012).
- Labor Intensity: Poultry farming requires significant labor, which can be demanding for farmers. The need for constant attention to feeding, cleaning, and management can be challenging, especially for small-scale farmers (Berg, 2001).

Enforcement:

- Regulatory Support: Governments and regulatory bodies play a critical role in supporting poultry farmers. Policies and programs aimed at improving biosecurity, providing veterinary services, and managing environmental impacts are essential for enhancing the sustainability of poultry farming (Indian Government, 2014-15; African Competition Forum, 2014).
- Training and Education: Providing training and education on best practices in poultry farming can help address some of the constraints and disadvantages. Programs focusing on disease management, biosecurity, and efficient production methods are vital for improving farm performance and sustainability (Marmelstein et al., 2024).
- Market Stabilization: Implementing measures to stabilize poultry markets and provide financial support during periods of crisis can help mitigate the effects of market fluctuations and ensure the economic viability of poultry enterprises (Singh et al., 2022).

5.2. Analysis of Sociological Aspects:

This analysis explores the sociological implications of poultry keeping among Brahmin caste farmers in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal. By examining the socio-cultural, economic, and community aspects of poultry farming, we aim to understand how this entrepreneurial activity influences the lives of these farmers and their broader social environment.

- Cultural Practices: Poultry keeping among Brahmin caste farmers in the Mid-Terai region is influenced by traditional cultural practices and beliefs. Brahmins, traditionally known for their roles in religious and academic pursuits, may approach poultry farming with a unique set of values and expectations. The integration of poultry farming into their livelihoods reflects a shift from traditional roles to more diverse economic activities, potentially challenging traditional norms but also providing new opportunities for social mobility.
- Social Status: In the Brahmin community, which traditionally values education and religious practices over commercial activities, engaging in poultry farming can impact social status. Success in poultry keeping can enhance the social standing of individual farmers, demonstrating adaptability and entrepreneurial spirit. Conversely, failure or challenges in poultry farming might affect the perceived social prestige, highlighting the complex interplay between economic success and social status.
- Income Generation: Poultry keeping significantly contributes to the income of Brahmin farmers in the Mid-Terai region. The ability to generate substantial income from poultry farming can lead to improved living standards, access to better education, and healthcare for the farmers and their families. This economic boost often translates into greater social mobility, allowing Brahmin families to invest in their children's education and engage in community development activities.
- Employment Opportunities: Poultry farming creates direct and indirect employment opportunities within the community. The need for labor in managing poultry farms provides jobs for local workers, including family members and others from nearby villages. This employment opportunity can contribute to reducing rural unemployment and fostering economic development within the community.
- Community Integration: Poultry farming can enhance community integration by fostering new social interactions and networks. Farmers often collaborate and share knowledge with other poultry keepers, creating a support system that strengthens community bonds. These interactions can lead to the formation of cooperatives or informal networks that facilitate resource sharing and collective problem-solving.
- Knowledge Exchange: The practice of poultry farming encourages the exchange of knowledge and skills among farmers. Experienced poultry keepers often share their expertise with newcomers, contributing to the overall improvement of farming practices and the development of a knowledge-sharing culture within the community.
- Disease and Economic Vulnerability: Poultry farming in the Mid-Terai region is susceptible to various challenges, such as disease outbreaks. These challenges can have significant social implications, as widespread disease can lead to financial losses and economic instability for farmers. The economic vulnerability experienced due to poultry diseases can strain social relationships and create stress within families and communities.
- Market Fluctuations: The instability in poultry markets, with fluctuating prices for eggs and meat, can impact the economic stability of farmers. Market fluctuations can create uncertainties and stress, affecting the social well-being of farmers and their families. The need for market stability and support systems becomes crucial to mitigate these challenges.
- Adaptation Strategies: Brahmin farmers in the Mid-Terai region demonstrate resilience by adapting their poultry farming practices to changing conditions. Strategies such as diversification of poultry breeds, adoption of improved management

practices, and seeking external support reflect the farmers' ability to navigate challenges and enhance their socio-economic well-being.

- **Support Systems:** The development of support systems, including government policies, extension services, and community organizations, plays a critical role in supporting poultry farmers. These support systems help address the challenges faced by farmers, promoting sustainable poultry farming and contributing to the overall socio-economic development of the community.

5.3 Income and Profit Analysis:

Seasonal Income:

- Over a typical three-month season, a poultry farm with 100 broiler chickens generates an income of NRs. 2,50,000 (two lakh and fifty thousand). This income is derived from the sale of broilers, which typically involves selling the birds once they reach market weight. This figure reflects the gross revenue from poultry sales before deducting any operational costs.

Cost Considerations and Net Profit:

- The net profit for this operation is significantly influenced by various cost factors. Key expenditures include costs for feed, medication, management, and other operational expenses. The analysis indicates that by reducing costs associated with medicine, management, and feeding, the net profit can be optimized. After accounting for these costs, the net profit for the three-month period is reported to be NRs. 80,000 (eighty thousand). This net profit reflects the remaining amount after subtracting the total costs from the gross income.

Annual Earnings and Profit:

- On an annual basis, the poultry farm generates earnings in the range of NRs. 8–9 lakh (eight to nine lakh). This includes the cumulative income from multiple seasons throughout the year. The annual net profit is noted to be NRs. 3,20,000 (three lakh twenty thousand). This annual net profit is a crucial metric for assessing the financial health of the poultry enterprise, highlighting the profitability after covering all operating expenses.

Employment Impact:

- The poultry farming operation provides full-time employment for a two-person household, typically involving a husband and wife. This employment not only supports the livelihoods of these individuals but also contributes to the local economy by creating job opportunities. The presence of two full-time positions underscores the labor-intensive nature of poultry farming and the role it plays in providing stable income for the family.

Vulnerability to Disease Outbreaks:

- A critical factor influencing the financial stability of poultry farming is the risk of disease outbreaks. The study highlights that in the event of a pandemic disease or significant health issue affecting the poultry stock, there can be severe financial repercussions. Disease outbreaks can lead to high mortality rates among the poultry, resulting in substantial economic losses. This risk underscores the importance of effective disease management strategies and biosecurity measures to protect the poultry from infectious diseases and ensure the continuity of the business.

5.4 Policy Recommendations for Advancing Poultry Farming in Nepal:

Given the current state of poultry farming in Nepal, particularly in the Mid-Terai region, several policy recommendations can be made to enhance the sector's productivity, sustainability, and economic impact. Drawing from recent literature and industry insights, the following recommendations aim to address key challenges and leverage opportunities for growth.

Enhance Disease Management and Biosecurity:

Recommendation:

- Implement robust disease management programs and enhance biosecurity measures across poultry farms.
Rationale: Disease outbreaks pose a significant risk to poultry farming, leading to substantial financial losses and jeopardizing the sustainability of the industry. Effective vaccination programs, regular health check-ups, and strict biosecurity protocols are crucial to mitigate these risks.

Actions:

- Develop and subsidize comprehensive vaccination and disease prevention programs.
- Establish local veterinary clinics or mobile health units to provide timely medical care and advice.
- Educate farmers on best practices for biosecurity and disease management through workshops and training sessions (Mishra, 2023; Mishra, 2024).

Support Financial Accessibility and Cost Reduction:

Recommendation:

- Provide financial support mechanisms and incentives to reduce the cost burden on poultry farmers.
Rationale: High production costs, including feed, medicine, and management expenses, impact profitability. Financial support can help mitigate these costs and improve the economic viability of poultry farming.

Actions:

- Introduce subsidies or low-interest loans for purchasing feed, medicines, and other essential inputs (Mishra & Chaudhary, 2021).
- Implement tax breaks or financial incentives for poultry farmers who adopt cost-effective and sustainable practices.

Foster Technological Innovation and Adoption:

Recommendation:

- Promote the adoption of modern technologies and innovations in poultry farming.
Rationale: Technological advancements can enhance productivity, improve feed efficiency, and reduce labor intensity. Embracing Industry 4.0 concepts and other technological innovations can help modernize the sector (Mishra, Nepal & Aithal, 2022).

Actions:

- Support research and development in poultry farming technologies and provide grants for innovation.
- Facilitate training programs to help farmers adopt new technologies, such as automated feeding systems and health monitoring tools.

Improve Market Access and Stabilization:

Recommendation:

- Develop infrastructure and policies to stabilize markets and improve access for poultry products.
Rationale: Market fluctuations and instability can negatively affect poultry farmers' income. Improved infrastructure and market policies can help stabilize prices and ensure better market access.

Actions:

- Establish cold storage facilities and improve transportation infrastructure to reduce post-harvest losses and ensure consistent product availability.
- Implement price stabilization mechanisms and provide market intelligence to help farmers make informed decisions.

Promote Sustainable Practices and Environmental Management:

Recommendation:

- Encourage sustainable poultry farming practices to minimize environmental impact.
Rationale: Intensive poultry farming can have negative environmental effects, such as waste management issues and greenhouse gas emissions. Adopting sustainable practices can help mitigate these impacts.

Actions:

- Promote waste management solutions, such as composting and recycling poultry litter.
- Support research on sustainable feed options and environmentally friendly farming practices.

6. Conclusion:

The study reveals that a poultry farm with 100 broiler chickens in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal can achieve a gross income of NRs. 2,50,000 per season and an annual earning of NRs. 8–9 lakh. After accounting for costs, the net profit per season stands at NRs. 80,000, and the annual net profit totals NRs. 3,20,000. The operation provides full-time employment for two individuals, contributing to their economic stability. However, the financial success of the poultry farm is susceptible to risks, particularly from disease outbreaks, which can lead to significant losses and threaten the sustainability of the business. Addressing these vulnerabilities through improved disease management and cost control measures is essential for ensuring the long-term viability and profitability of poultry farming in the region. Poultry farming in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal, particularly among Brahmin caste farmers, presents a complex array of advantages and benefits that significantly impact the local socio-economic landscape. This analysis underscores that while poultry farming offers notable economic gains, employment opportunities, and improved nutritional outcomes, it also faces several constraints and disadvantages that must be addressed to ensure its long-term viability.

Advantages and Benefits:

Poultry farming stands out as a profitable agricultural activity for Brahmin farmers, with the potential to generate substantial income. For instance, a farm with 100 broiler poultry can yield an annual net profit of NRs. 3,20,000 (three lakh twenty thousand), offering considerable financial benefits. Beyond economic gains, poultry farming provides full-time employment for two household members, thus contributing to local employment and economic stability. Additionally, poultry products such as eggs and meat are essential sources of high-quality protein and vital nutrients, which are crucial for enhancing the nutritional standards of the community.

Constraints and Disadvantages:

Despite its advantages, poultry farming is not without its challenges. High production costs, including expenses for feed, vaccines, and management, can impact profitability. Disease management remains a significant issue, as the lack of access to veterinary services and effective disease control measures can lead to substantial losses. Environmental impacts from intensive poultry farming, such as waste management issues and greenhouse gas emissions, also pose challenges that need to be addressed.

Market fluctuations further complicate the economic stability of poultry farming. Price volatility can affect income predictability, making it difficult for farmers to maintain financial stability. Biosecurity risks associated with low biosecurity measures increase the likelihood of disease outbreaks, which can devastate poultry stocks. Additionally, the labor-intensive nature of poultry farming requires constant attention and effort, which can be demanding for small-scale farmers.

Enforcement and Support Mechanisms:

To overcome these challenges and support the sustainability of poultry farming, effective enforcement mechanisms are essential. Regulatory support is crucial for implementing policies that improve biosecurity, provide veterinary services, and manage environmental impacts. Training programs and educational initiatives on best practices in poultry farming can help farmers address issues related to disease management and efficient production. Market stabilization measures, such as financial support during crises and strategies to reduce price volatility, are also important for ensuring the economic viability of poultry enterprises.

Sociological Impact:

The sociological analysis of poultry keeping among Brahmin caste farmers reveals a multifaceted impact on their social environment. Poultry farming influences cultural practices, social status, and community dynamics. It integrates with local traditions and can enhance social cohesion through shared practices and community support. However, the challenges associated with poultry farming, such as disease outbreaks and market instability, can affect the economic vulnerability of farmers and their social standing.

Understanding these sociological aspects is critical for developing support systems and policies that address both the benefits and challenges of poultry farming. By fostering a supportive environment through targeted interventions, it is possible to enhance the sustainability and socio-economic impact of poultry farming in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal.

In summary, poultry farming in the Mid-Terai region of Nepal offers significant benefits, including economic gains, employment, and nutritional improvements. However, it also faces substantial constraints and disadvantages, such as high production costs, disease management issues, and market fluctuations. Effective enforcement mechanisms and support systems are essential for addressing these challenges and ensuring the long-term viability of poultry enterprises. By considering the sociological impacts and implementing comprehensive support measures, it is possible to enhance the sustainability and positive impact of poultry farming for Brahmin farmers and the wider community.

7. Acknowledgement:

Thanks to the Gaurishankar campus, Bara Teachers and management committee for their support for research. This is academic learning exercise at the college to fulfil the dream of students of the college to learn and write with best scientist of business and management Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra in Nepal who believes in impact of research in society rather than impact factor.

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